

TRANSFORMATIVE LEARNING: PROMOTING LEARNERS' CRITICAL-THINKING SKILLS AND KNOWLEDGE BY ENHANCING APPLICABLE APPROACHES IN EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: *The goals of transformative learning are to affect the social, ecological, economic, and technological potentials of humanity in the world by targeting great destinations. Transformative learning is the best strategic approach to reach success by using valuable and creative tools and it promotes lifelong beliefs and hopes as well as targets not only with continuing or also with developing phenomena which we have thought controversial dilemma in the field of education. It is the main step for shifting the students' actions into transformative learning as it appeared by their perspectives, their initiatives, and their answers to the level or logical questions. Any person was not created as a dumb; everyone has their creative sides, smart horizon, and superb capacity which are not similar to each other, even if they are convinced and believe in themselves, they have just pushed their mind to work out and to release great motives. Providing learners with opportunities to think deeply and critically about complex issues is essential for the development of their critical-thinking skills (Brookfield, 2012). By engaging in rigorous analysis and reflection, learners can enhance their ability to evaluate information, identify biases, and make well-informed decisions. Moreover, low expectations can be controversial points when a person can not believe and have dumb statements.*

Keywords: *Transformative learning, Critical reflection, Critical-thinking, Rational disclosure, Centrality of experience.*

Main part: Transformative learning is a theory and process that involves a profound shift in perspective and understanding, leading to personal growth and the development of critical thinking skills. It was initially proposed by Jack Mezirow, an influential adult education theorist, but has since been embraced and expanded upon by numerous scholars in various disciplines. At its core, transformative learning involves a critical examination of one's assumptions, beliefs, and values, often precipitated by a disorienting dilemma or a significant life event. Through reflection and introspection, learners reframe their existing mental frameworks and construct new meanings and interpretations of their experiences. Transformative learning is a pedagogical approach that encourages learners to critically examine their assumptions, beliefs, and values, leading to a shift in their perspectives and the development of critical-thinking skills (Mezirow, 1991). This process involves challenging existing cognitive structures and engaging in reflective thinking.

The transformative learning theory has 3 basic elements that facilitate the learning and transformation of students in the learning environment. They are critical reflection, the centrality of experience, and rational discourse. Transformative experience might be anything from an adult who transforms own capacity to share opinion after learning something from people on the way view life due to a traumatic experience. An applicable approach to promoting critical-thinking skills involves incorporating real-world contexts and problem-solving tasks into the learning process (Perkins & Saloman, 2012). By relating the learning content to practical situations, learners are encouraged to apply their critical-thinking abilities and develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Critical reflection happens when someone needs to think critically about their experiences, which in turn leads to self-awareness and supports the stage of comprehension. According to Mezirow (1991), transformative learning encompasses the process by which learners reframe their perspectives and engage in reflective thinking to critically examine their assumptions, beliefs, and values. This shift in cognitive structures is essential for promoting critical thinking skills.

Rational disclosure, mostly occurs in discussion with other people that focuses on personal and socially held truths and hopes which are emphasized as a root of thinking logically and as well as rational manner.

The centrality of experience is the last component of Mezirow's transformative learning theory, such practices contain what students do, what they hope or are certain, the way that they react to real situation, their expectations, and their perspective. This transformation enables individuals to view themselves and the world in a different light, cultivating increased self-awareness, empathy, and the ability to think critically about complex issues. Key elements of transformative learning include reflective practice, dialogue, and social interaction. Learners engage in deep reflection on their experiences, question their long-held beliefs, and actively seek out new knowledge and perspectives. The process is often facilitated through structured dialogues and discussions with others who hold diverse viewpoints, which challenges and expands existing mental models. By engaging in these dialogues, learners can explore alternative perspectives and develop a more comprehensive understanding of complex subjects. Transformative learning has been applied in various educational settings, including adult education, higher education, and professional development. It is particularly relevant in contexts where learners must grapple with societal issues, navigate personal growth, or adapt to rapidly changing environments. By fostering critical thinking, self-reflection, and empathy, transformative learning equips individuals with the skills and mindset necessary to navigate complex challenges and contribute to positive social change. While the concept of transformative learning is well-established, it continues to evolve and be refined by scholars in the field. Several influential names in transformative learning research include Jack Mezirow, Edward Taylor, Patricia Cranton, and Kathleen P. King. Exploring their works and the related literature will provide a deeper understanding of transformative learning theory, its application, and its implications for education and personal development. Educators can help learners push them to act in a creative atmosphere by using logical, problem-solving, or even simple devices or exercises and find their creative sides as they had a

long time from birth time. Experience and failure can cause only achievement which is needed to face assessing processes. When we scrutinize their improvement of thinking we can start another stage which is defined as critical reflections with multiple intelligences: intelligence denied, intelligence regained and defining intelligence. Transformational learning has been analyzed with different practices in the field of education. It can be improved by a variety of learning approaches to establish creative thinking ways. Moreover, emancipator learning plays a crucial role in demonstrating democratic conditions on students' behavior or learning outcomes by comparing psychological models, structural models and post-structural models. Emancipator learning is just examining critically and knowing the value of the group or society's power. It enhances adults' thinking way and willingness to learn which has a positive effect on work via engaging them in critical thinking or dialogue and of course their reflection on the topic or subject.

Conclusion: Adults have a variety of receiving and learning skills that are differentiated from each other. Some of them tend to work individually: such as doing course requirements and assignments and work hard under pressure to overcome positive results in their learning process. Moreover, they get used to doing requirements by using all kinds of capacities and thinking imaginatively, it can be a solo way to imitate the challenge by obtaining a great experience or just improve critical reflection by being autonomous. On the other side of the coin, approaching success is much more easily and more effective by reaching all outcomes through socializing, like group or teamwork. In transformative Learning, both phenomena have been given clearly and proved with some examples. However, it is crucial to note that, to facilitate transformative learning students need to participate in whole group debates and discussions and need to be more open to the activities to enhance their skills and knowledge. They can obtain full information about a topic or can evaluate their perspective, can judge themselves in terms of knowledge, can explain the tough situation practically and can improve their point of view as well as their creative thinking way by observing other group mates. Transformative learning, in my point of view, is more valuable to participating class learning environment through the group, enlarging own practical knowledge, arriving at reflective learning outcomes etc.

Reference List:

1. Baildon, M., & Damico, J. S. (2017). Transformative Teaching in the Twenty-First Century: Innovations for Inclusive Education.
2. Brookfield, S. D. (2012). Teaching for critical thinking: Tools and techniques to help students question their assumptions.
3. Mezirow, J. (1991). Transformative dimensions of adult learning.
4. Perkins, D. N., & Salomon, G. (2012). Knowledge to go: A motivational plan for promoting student engagement with intellectual skills.
5. Baildon, M., & Damico, J. S. (2017). Transformative Teaching in the Twenty-First Century: Innovations for Inclusive Education.
6. Tong, J., "Transformative Pedagogy" [video based on Cohen (1997) [Transformative Pedagogy](#) [Links to an external site.](#)]
7. E.J.Tisdell. 2012. Themes and Variations to Transformational Learning.
8. Sherry Sullivan. 2014. Emancipatory: The different types of adult learning.
9. J. Code, R. Ralph and K. Forde. 25.02.2022. "A Disorienting Dilemma: Teaching and learning in Technology Education during a Time of Crisis."